

Luca Danieli, Ph.D. Senior Scientist
Websites: lucadanieli.org | slidingdoors-official.com
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Allegations of a Hostile Research Environment at the University of Music and Performing Arts Graz (KUG)

This personal investigation is released as a rebuttal to an official statement published by a research team on the website of the University of Music and Performing Arts Graz (KUG). In that statement, the team characterized the prior statements of the postdoc researcher as illegitimate whistleblowing and an unjustified obstruction of their research. Specifically, the statement claims:

“The PI granted the PDR the opportunity to implement his own ideas within the scope of his project work, provided he also participated (to a correspondingly limited extent) in the ongoing research of the rest of the team (PI and DR1). Throughout the entire project duration, the PDR was able to develop his ideas completely freely, without any interference from the PI or the rest of the project team.” (Original statement in German)

It is the opinion of the postdoc that such a statement is contradicted by the available evidence, as he reports the presence of multiple emails in which the PI indicated his expectation to capitalize on the whole workforce available in his ongoing research, therefore not giving time to the postdoc researcher to actually implement his ideas as claimed.

They also refer to previous reviews by multiple organizations and, specifically, to a prior preliminary review by the Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI) regarding the authorship of a published article to claim a “clear state of affairs.” However, this preliminary decision was issued without providing the postdoctoral researcher the opportunity to respond to the facts presented by the research team or to provide a rebuttal before the decision was issued.

Since the release of eventual false claims in an official webpage of a public university characterizing the actions of the postdoc researcher as “illegitimate whistleblowing” and “obstruction of research” have, in the view of the postdoc researcher, the effect of diminishing his scientific reputation, the postdoc researcher has in a first instance submitted a request to the ÖAWI to review the case. Specifically, the GWP guidelines on Good Scientific Practice report at §3 para. 2 no. 5 unfounded accusations of violations of the standards of Good Scientific Practice as a type of misconduct.

The ÖAWI has declined to open an investigation reporting that such submission mixed old and new allegations, and such a submission could not be considered for not meeting the standard requirements [see evidence 24 in the attached document presenting summaries of available evidence]. For this reason, as the main organization investigating these types of issues in Austria has declined to open an investigation to factually verify the claims, and the only other type of action I may have consist in going to court and I don't have the money because I don't have a job

since 2 years (also due to dedicating my 2025 to mental health after a strong breakdown deriving from my previous whistleblowing), this public report remains the only viable path to accountability. Furthermore, as the ÖAWI is a private association rather than a public administrative body, its procedures are not formally governed by the same statutory requirements of transparency and administrative law that apply to public institutions. I present herein an investigation on the topic.

While the statement published on the project website may represent the individual initiative of the PI, its hosting on a public university platform gives it a veneer of institutional authority. Given that official oversight bodies (ÖAWI) have declined to resolve the documented contradictions between this statement and the available evidence, the researcher is left with no choice but to provide this factual rebuttal. In accordance with the principles of the right to reply and the protection of professional reputation, this transparency is essential to address the public characterization of the researcher's conduct.

This investigation serves as a factual record to address the public characterizations made against his scientific conduct and to ensure that the procedural obstacles which prevented a formal resolution are documented. In the absence of an accessible judicial or administrative review, providing this transparency is a matter of public interest regarding the oversight of research integrity and the preservation of research freedom. Furthermore, it serves as a formal call for the university and responsible authorities to fulfill their accountability by conducting a thorough investigation to clarify the facts and resolve the existing evidentiary contradictions.

CONTEXTUAL INFORMATION

In 2020, postdoc researcher Luca Danieli was invited by the University of Music and Performing Arts Graz (KUG) to develop a project proposal for a Lise Meitner program, a 2-year fund offered by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) to attract and promote the career development of exceptionally qualified young researchers who could contribute to the scientific development of an Austrian research institution by working at it.

Shortly before submitting, the mentor proposed to change the destination of the project from a Lise Meitner program to a Stand-alone Project program, as a way to extend the project to three years and support a Ph.D. student of his, suggesting that the postdoc researcher would still lead the project. To do so, the mentor should be listed as PI.

The project's core hypothesis was framed around the concept of entropy, and intended to investigate cadential phenomena in music "through a phenomenological inquiry based on the concept of entropy (2.1) that describes a tendency to move from states of order to states of disorder" (p. 7).

The project became operative on 1.3.2021.

Citations in squared brackets (e.g., [4]) refer to specific evidence summaries provided in the attached *List of Summaries*, which document the factual basis for this report.

PROMOTION OF YOUNG RESEARCHERS

Available evidence highlights the presence of a discussion before the change in destination of the project to the Stand-alone Project program. Evidence [6] highlights the presence of a letter submitted from the postdoc researcher to the PI on 16.4.2022 stating that the PI had suggested before submission that the postdoc researcher would have led the project. In a following response [7] dated 19.4.2022, the PI confirms the statement of the researcher.

My investigation highlights that the new version of the project proposal submitted to the Stand-alone Project program incorporated a new foreseen output, that consisted in the researcher's writing up of a monograph to possibly serve as a habilitation (p. 13). Highlighted that (i) the intellectual work of the postdoc researcher in conceiving and developing the proposal was originally directed toward the explicit goal of developing his own research ideas, and (ii) the presence of a prior understanding on project leadership before submitting the proposal, the effective inclusion of this specific output in the final project description indicates that the promotion of the researcher's career remained a formal objective of the project, notwithstanding the change in PI.

HOSTILE RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT

As the promotion of the researcher's ideas arguably remained informing the submitted project, with the stated goal of leading to the preparation of a monograph, it is a question whether the researcher had to be provided with research autonomy. Available evidence highlights that soon after the project started, the PI criticized the researcher's ideas regarding entropy as a driving research framework for the project [4]. Evidence [6] and [7] show the following unilateral change in leadership chosen by the PI. It is important to note that these ideas linking entropy and cadences through a motion from states of order to ones of disorder informed the original approach reported in the approved proposal, and were later published in the *Journal of New Music Research* (Volume 51, Issue 4-5), with an editorial mentioning the innovative character and relative potential impact of the research.

Specifically, it becomes apparent that this was not an isolated dismissive comment, as in evidence [7] the PI cited as "unhelpful" most of the researcher's inputs in the project. This attitude is consistent with the subsequent dismissal of repeated warnings raised by the postdoc researcher about the scientific reliability of the research methodology. It is a fact that today, a scientific journal has opened an investigation into one of the articles emerging from the project directed by the PI, after the postdoc researcher reported concerns about its scientific reliability, suggesting that those concerns were eventually grounded and should have at least deserved attention.

Given the stated intention for the project to potentially result in a monograph that could serve as a habilitation for the postdoc researcher, it is unclear what this monograph should have been talking about since the postdoc researcher had restricted power in influencing the project's methodology. In particular, if the concerns about the reliability of the research methodology raised by the postdoc researcher would happen to be reasonable, it is a question whether the researcher was intended to use this data, eventually resulting in conscious violation of research integrity.

It is important to highlight therefore whether the postdoc researcher was eventually provided with freedom to research on his own ideas within the framework of the project, at least on a part-time basis. In this case, evidence [7, 8, 9, 10] highlights a discussion between the PI and the postdoc researcher regarding workload and the possibility for the researcher to dedicate appropriate time to his own ideas. This evidence reports at least one sentence highlighting discontent from the PI regarding the time spent by the researcher in the project, which was considered not enough and explicitly asked the postdoc researcher to dedicate more time in the project led by the PI. Specifically, the PI initially agreed with the proposal of the researcher to grant him research autonomy two days per week, but deferred this to the future after the identification of a student assistant, stating that he currently needed all workforce in the project. In a following email, to the proposal of the researcher to reduce his employment to two days per week to be spent on his own research—thereby freeing budget/time for an additional postdoc researcher to support the work of the PI—, the PI characterized this option as illogical, stating that he was expecting all workforce in his project.

Evidence [5] also highlights the presence of an email from the PI forwarding a 2-year postdoc opportunity at McGill University to the postdoc researcher. It should be noted that at the time when this email was sent, the researcher still had 2 years of contract with KUG. Given the geographic location in Canada (contrasted with the researcher's base in Europe) and the researcher's existing contract, this can hardly be considered as an opportunity for career advancement but rather an alternative. In this sense, this evidence suggests that the PI was promoting the premature exit of the researcher from the project.

Overall, the available evidence highlights the presence of a hostile research environment, starting with the critique of the researcher's ideas that informed the original hypotheses of the approved grant proposal, moving to the continuous dismissal of scientific inputs and subsequent reproach of not contributing enough, to the pressure of dedicating less and less time to his research autonomy until the expectation to dedicate the full workload to the PI's project and the eventual promotion of a premature exit.

LACK OF CONSIDERATION OF EVIDENCE DURING THE INVESTIGATION PROCESS

Available evidence shows that part of the available evidence informing the period 2021-2022 has never been accounted for by the authorities delegated with the investigation of scientific misconduct. Specifically, evidence [11, 12] shows that after contacting the University Ombudsman, this did not request a formal allegation and based his preliminary judgement on an email exchange that was currently happening after his involvement. Specifically, the preliminary investigation of the University Ombudsman reports that no misconduct was found because the FWF guidelines grant decision power to the PI, and that "most issues should have been agreed on before submitting the project." However, the University Ombudsman did not investigate whether an understanding was in place before submitting the project.

After being redirected to the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) for a more thorough investigation [12], the FWF requested the redaction of all personal correspondence, as it could not be considered without the agreement of the PI for procedural reasons regarding data protection [14].

This requirement for redaction effectively prevented the investigation from reviewing the primary evidence regarding the original understanding on project lead. Evidence highlights that on 20.11.2025 [28], the postdoc researcher asked for clarification about the specific legal references that prevented them from considering part of the submitted evidence, but he received a simple statement mentioning that all ÖAWI procedures were correctly followed. The researcher highlighted a procedural discrepancy: the ÖAWI does not typically mandate the redaction of personal correspondence; it therefore remains unclear why this evidence was restricted in a review involving potential academic misconduct.

The following appeal to the ÖAWI was accepted but, during the investigation process, the committee chose to not investigate the allegations for the period before the FWF complaint, restricting their investigation to a subset of evidence happening after such a period. Eventually, the ÖAWI found no misconduct, characterizing the allegations as “partially misleading and inaccurate.”

EXCLUSION FROM THE PROJECT AND MISSING PROFILE INCIDENT

Available evidence shows that, after the postdoc researcher contacted the Funding Agency, the PI excluded the researcher from the project, citing an emerging lack of trust and a divergence of opinion about the chosen methodology that could not allow any further collaboration. After the termination of the researcher’s employment, the PI states he removed the profile picture of the postdoc researcher from the website, while leaving the picture of all the other current and ex team members on the team. The Vice-Rector for Research and Quality Management archived the episode as an “oversight,” without providing evidential proof suggesting that the episode was an oversight.

FAILURE TO GUARANTEE THE PROMOTION OF YOUNG RESEARCHERS

Given the context of promotion of young researchers originating the project proposal, the Funding Agency (FWF) proposed two options to resolve the conflict: the first consisted in a collaborative work plan to allow the postdoc researcher to implement his ideas within the framework of the project; the second consisted in the possibility for the postdoc researcher to apply for the ESPRIT program [15]. However, entrance to the ESPRIT program was not guaranteed [27]. Eventually, the duration of the procedural disagreements and the eventual exclusion from the project meant that the researcher did not have the full 5-year eligibility window at his disposal for the development and submission of the application. This significantly reduced the time available for a viable transition into this independent career path compared to the standard timeframe afforded to early-career researchers.

Toward the end of his employment, the researcher submitted an article to a conference to be held after the termination of his contract. Evidence shows that the researcher requested support for these costs from the Funding Agency, the University, and the PI, but all parties refused [29], effectively withdrawing support for the researcher’s professional dissemination at the conclusion of the project. This refusal is particularly noteworthy as evidence indicates that the PI simultaneously sought a budget extension to continue the project for other team members while

excluding the postdoc researcher from similar support. This suggests that, despite the presence of a tentative solution suggested by the FWF in their decision, mechanisms for his promotion were not guaranteed.

CONCLUSION

Overall, the documented evidence illustrates a systematically dismissive environment. This began with the denial of the research autonomy that originally informed the project's conception and escalated into the researcher's exclusion from the project after reporting these concerns to the Funding Agency. The subsequent removal of the researcher's profile from the project website—an action applied uniquely to the postdoc researcher—intensifies the presence of an environment hostile toward the postdoc researcher.

Together with the following failure to guarantee the proposed mechanisms for the promotion of the young researcher, the episode raises questions as to whether the institutional Duty of Care (*Fürsorgepflicht*) was correctly implemented. This includes the duty to provide a functional workplace and to protect the employee from avoidable professional harm—including career development interests that informed the scope and origination of the proposal. In this context, it is noted that the Austrian Supreme Court has observed a legal principle (OGH 9ObA131/11x) stating that while an employee must comply with justified instructions, the employer is obligated to protect the employee's interests; where these conflict, a balancing of interests is required when assessing whether instructions were justified. It is of particular relevance that the core hypotheses the researcher attempted to implement were an integral part of the granted proposal; the subsequent dismissal of these ideas by the PI brings into question whether this criticism and the subsequent restrictions on the researcher's research autonomy were justified.

The fact that a scientific journal has now opened an investigation into the reliability of the project's data furthermore suggests that the researcher's criticisms were not unmotivated. This raises significant questions on whether the following exclusion of the researcher was a justified action or whether the researcher was simply expected to comply with directions regardless of their scientific or ethical implications.

ADDITIONAL

My investigation further extends to the behavior of the Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI) as an oversight body. Particularly a concern from the perspective of research integrity should be raised about the fact that the ÖAWI pronounced a preliminary judgment about authorship without granting representation to all parties involved, and further provided the research team with a special permission to bypass traditional confidentiality to communicate this preliminary decision to the editor of a scientific journal [24]. This raises a procedural concern regarding equal representation, as the preliminary judgment was reached and communicated to a third-party editor without providing the postdoc researcher an opportunity to respond to the research team's characterization of the facts.